

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Citizen Observer Training: “How to do research” and CO Toolbox

Work Package 3, Deliverable D3.1

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Please refer to this report as follows:

Sweeney, L., Kozłowska, A., Vuckovic, M. (2023). Citizen Observer Training: “How to do research” and CO toolbox. Deliverable D3.1 of the Horizon Europe project GREENGAGE.

Project information	
Project name:	GREENGAGE – Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
Grant Agreement No.	101086530
Start date:	01/01/2023
Duration:	36 months
Coordinator:	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology Giefinggasse 4, 1210 Vienna, Austria
Contact:	Jan Peters-Anders, Research Engineer
	Funded by the European Union GA n° 101086530.
Deliverable details	
Description:	This deliverable covers T3.2 and T3.4 and includes scientific training and user manuals for GREENGAGE’s toolset.
Version:	Final
Dissemination level:	PU (Public)
Due date:	31/12/2023
Submission:	20/01/2024
Resubmission	15/11/2024
Lead:	Knowle West Media Centre (KWMC)
Author(s):	Sweeney, L. (KWMC), UK Kozłowska, A. (AIT), Austria Vuckovic, M. (VRVIS), Austria

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List of Acronyms

AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
BCC	Bristol City Council
Borghi	I Borghi piu Belli D’Italia
BUAS	Breda University of Applied Sciences
CO	Citizen Observatory
COs	Citizen Observatories
CObs	Citizen Observers

EBLN	The East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood
EU	European Union
GEB	GREENGAGE Ethics Board
IA	Innovation Action
IAB	Innovation Action Board
KB	Knowledge Base
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KWMC	Knowle West Media Centre
PNRR	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
PSTs	Pilot Support Teams
UWE	University of the West of England

Glossary

Citizen Observatory	According to EU project WeObserve, “Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance.” [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework] In GREENGAGE is a place like a <i>Living Lab</i> (a laboratory in a real context, putting stakeholders at the centre of the process) for collective learning that exploits the opportunity of using sensors and the use of Earth observation technology where citizens collect data and are empowered by the information generated from these data to improve environmental management towards an innovative governance of the territory.
Citizen Science	“In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making” (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).
GREEN Engine	The GREEN Engine is the set of tools and software applications that make up the GREENGAGE toolset. They will be used to support the GREENGAGE COs in fulfilling the objectives of the Innovation Pilots.
Innovation Action Board	The Innovation Action Board (IAB) is a collaborative and interdisciplinary team comprising partner representatives with expertise in technologies and citizen participation, who oversee the whole GREENGAGE Innovation Action and steer the Pilot Support Teams.
Living Lab	According to the European Network of Living Labs, “Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders.”
Pilot Support Teams	The Pilot Support Teams (PSTs) are interdisciplinary groups of partner representatives that assist the five pilot initiatives in developing their use cases and foster the constitution of functioning GREENGAGE COs as Living Labs. The PSTs shall achieve a deeper understanding of the local necessities and support

	in-depth discussions on technical solutions and social enablers accordingly. PSTs are the local operational link with Pilots and aim to foster feedback and responsiveness to ensure the development of the COs.
The GREENGAGE Academy	The GREENGAGE Academy hosts the emerging GREENGAGE Community of Practise and is the central platform for sharing understandings of the process of developing GREENGAGE COs. As such, the Academy serves as the central interaction platform between CO coordinators, citizen observers and other participants of COs. The Academy acts as a knowledge base around the setting up and effective coordination of citizen observatories. The Academy stores and indexes training resources, MOOCs, success stories, findings and best practises collected from the four GREENGAGE pilots, but also those generated or adapted to guide the setting up of the pilots
The GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework	The GREENGAGE CO (Citizen Observatory) methodological framework suggests core concepts, processes and guidelines on how to develop COs in GREENGAGE in ways that are ethical, democratic and responsive to common urban challenges and their situational manifestations in five pilots.
Thematic Co-Explorations	A Thematic Co-Explorations involves a group of people that combines already available datasets (Open Data, Copernicus) with those datasets that citizenry can contribute with. The idea is that heterogenous datasets are combined and correlated to give place to indicators and visualisations that are widely understandable by laypeople. Besides, the conclusions or insights driven by each pilot will be mapped into storylines, i.e., narrative and visual communication to raise awareness about the issues associated to Green Deal and possible solutions that as society we can tackle.
Use Cases	Generally, use cases are specific situations in which a product or service could potentially be used. In GREENGAGE we experiment in place-based, co-created and living platforms and learn about the useability of GREENGAGE COs as mediators of urban policy innovation. The products that are tested on their usefulness for driving transformative urban planning are existing technologies, tools and practices that brought into play by the GREENGAGE consortium to build tech-aided and co-created environmental monitoring and information systems, or GREENGAGE COs.

Executive summary (publishable)

This report documents how GREENGAGE approached the preparation of recruitment and training materials as well as the delivery of training of those stakeholders who have been involved in setting up GREENGAGE Observatories (GOs). As GOs address urban planning challenges in their interrelation between environmental, social-economic and political conditions, stakeholders require multi-disciplinary and context sensitive training to engage in collaborative research and innovation experiments. Given the timeframe of the project delivery and significant differences between the pilots, GREENGAGE suggests a 2-phased-approach on training to meet these guiding principles. The 1st phase focussed on the training of pilot owners as potential trainers once Observers are onboarded to the process of collaborative research and innovation. Both tasks – recruitment or onboarding and training – are seen as key for activating and equipping GOs across GREENGAGE. Given the time of delivery, the report reflects on these tasks only in terms of *near-term requirements* for enabling the research in GOs, focussing on setting up the basic technological and conceptual infrastructure for GOs (Toolbox, Academy, Engine) and documenting the accompanying re-structuring of the GREENGAGE website to make these accessible. Pilot specific scientific training materials and user manuals for GREENGAGE's toolset were not yet published at the time. As GOs, are set up as governance and policy labs, onboarding and enabling the meaningful contribution of GO participants is supposed to be an ongoing task and process of communities' engagement. Recruitment and training materials therefore need to be further developed based on the procedures for recruitment, training and ethics outlined here while the content and methods applied in developing materials can follow in response to the emerging experiments in the pilots. That's how GREENGAGE builds motivated and skilled teams of Observers, further supported by tailored training materials that can be used to build up interest in research and advocacy campaigns and ultimately ensure impactful communities-led science initiatives. All these enablers are documented in the GREENGAGE Toolbox. That's why, this report only provides preliminary insights into the process of onboarding and enabling of meaningful participation in GOs, unfolding around the aim of long-term capacity building for distinctive pathways of local transformations through GOs.

Related documents

- D1.9 – Ethical management plan and activities 1
- D2.1 – GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework
- D2.2 – Use cases and requirements analysis 1
- D2.6 – GREENGAGE technological requirements 1
- D3.2 – CO solution mapping to pilots, recruitment and training report
- D3.3 – GREENGAGE CO Academy Roadmap
- D4.1 – GREENGAGE Engine and manual 1
- D4.2 – GREENGAGE Engine and manual 2
- D7.1 – Plan for the communication, dissemination WP7 and exploitation of results 1

D7.4 - Project identity and branding

D7.5 - Project website and social media platforms

D7.6 - Package of dissemination materials 1

D7.7 - Package of dissemination materials 2

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to promote innovative governance processes, and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project will leverage citizens' participation and equip them with innovative digital solutions that will transform citizens' engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens will be inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The aim is to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This will be facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories will be a place where pilot cities will co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up process with top-down perspectives. This will provide the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aims to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The envisioned Citizen Observatory campaigns will be deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which will complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Object of the Deliverable

The deliverable *D3.1 Citizen Observer Training: “How to do research” and CO toolbox* is part of a set of three interrelated deliverables (D3.1, D3.2, D3.3) that aim to document how the GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework has been applied to prepare and activate pilot specific Citizen Observatories (COs).

This report details how the *Task 3.2 Preparing recruitment and training materials* and the *Task 3.4 Educate and train teams of Citizen Observers* have been realised through the distinct processes of “How To Do Research and the CO Toolbox”.

How To Do Research

The goal is to build sufficiently trained and resourced Citizen Observatories (COs) and Citizen Observers (COBs), including recruitment methods suitable for each pilot context, with an ethical approach to information collection that ensures inclusivity and diversity. In the short-term, this means equipping the individual pilots with the knowledge, resources, and techniques to successfully activate their COs. In the long-term these resources will feed into the GREENGAGE Knowledge Base and GREENGAGE White Book assets enabling future, COs even beyond the lifetime of the GREENGAGE project.

CO Toolbox (GREENGAGE Toolbox)

CO Toolbox, renamed during the project development to **GREENGAGE Toolbox**, is part of the GREEN Engine and one of the facilitators of the GREENGAGE Academy. It includes open datasets generated, new open-source tools developed, manuals and HOWTOs developed through the Citizen Observatories. It supports COBs in their research activities, with multimedia materials and manuals suited to their contexts and localities. This will be a suitable home for numerous materials created in the project and will serve as a useful repository beyond the lifetime of the project.

Along with D3.2 and D3.3, this deliverable provides initial evidence of applying Living Lab and citizen science solutions to address common urban challenges amidst diverse pilot opportunities and constraints.

3 Introduction

The distinguishing facet of the GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework is its emphasis on co-creation, situational onboarding of participants, and coordinating COs as Living Labs. This innovative approach goes beyond conventional methodologies, fostering an environment where dynamic collaboration thrives and where the existing situational contexts are respected. As such, the training, recruitment approaches, and toolbox documented here have been co-designed and co-adapted to suit the unique cultural, environmental, and social contexts of each pilot further enhancing their internal capabilities and knowledge.

Within *How To Do Research*, a two-step approach to training has been chosen, aiming to give pilots the adaptable tools and tailored knowledge to actively onboard COs themselves in suitable methods and contexts. Supporting materials are created throughout this process to support pilots' utilisations of tools and methods. These can be generalised across the project, thus reflecting on the general methods developed and used within the GREENGAGE project (further supporting the replication and upscaling) or made more specific to suit distinct pilots' needs, e.g., tailored to their use cases and their communities, adapted to local languages, etc.

The GREENGAGE Ethics Board underpins this activity with guidance and material on ethical standards, DEI, and use of tools.

After careful deliberations among the consortium members related to the need for a more centralized, user-friendly and accessible platform for disseminating information and engaging with the public, it was decided that the GREENGAGE website will be the home for all the developed content and the first port of call for citizens interested in the GREENGAGE project. A focus is put on accessibility and clarity of this content for a broader audience. Supplementary in-depth information about the individual Pilots' situational context and their planned CO activities (e.g., use cases/missions tackled in each CO), among other information, is provided on dedicated Pilot/CO pages within the main GREENGAGE website. This helps the essential Pilot/CO information being presented in a more concise way (e.g., collected and presented within one dedicated channel), hence more easily discoverable and accessible to a wide range of audiences.

4 How To Do Research

Equipping citizens with the knowledge and skills to effectively carry out research is vital to each CO's success. The aim is to create sustainable COs, capable of successful policy innovations, comprising of active, engaged, and knowledgeable citizens.

Drawing upon GREENGAGE consortium members KWMC and Ibercivis' expertise in community engagement and participatory methodologies, a two-stage training approach was formulated. First, a series of train-the-trainer workshops to efficiently develop local capacity amongst partners. Secondly, pilots themselves facilitating the onboarding and hands-on training of the citizens.

Leveraging the GREENGAGE's Methodological Framework, the formulation of the Innovation Action Board and Pilot Support Team groups (as outlined in D3.2) resulted in detailed situational analysis and activation plans for each pilot. This, along with a new understanding of the Citizen Observer Journey helped to define what needs to be sourced and developed regarding materials, approaches, tools, and training both project-wide and specific to COs; all underpinned by GREENGAGE's Ethics Framework, which aims to enable impactful, ethical participatory campaigns.

4.1 Training The Trainers

The first stage of the training approach focuses on developing a qualified group of trainers who can facilitate citizen onboarding. A series of weekly Train-the-Trainer workshops have been organised among the consortium members, comprising both formal training sessions as well as informal follow-ups focussed on practical implementations.

The sessions are led by domain experts from within the consortium and cover a wide range of topics integral to running an ethical, impactful citizen observatory. This includes introductions to data management, co-design methodologies, policymaking, GREEN Engine tools, and ethics considerations, making use of the materials developed throughout the project.

Following each session, informal gatherings provide opportunities for pilot owners to ask follow-up questions and get hands-on guidance in practically applying the concepts or tools. By participating in both theoretical and practical components, the pilots will gain well-rounded internal knowledge and proficiency.

In total, 11 formal workshops planned between December 2023 and March 2024, with 9 covering the aforementioned themes, and the final 2 sessions left open to be shaped by the pilots to address any remaining areas, as well as highlighting additional supporting materials to be developed, and any specific needs such as translations or other accommodations.

Once the Train-the-Trainer process is complete, the pilots will be prepared to share their knowledge and apply their expertise by onboarding and training citizens in their respective COs.

The materials developed will also be shared online on the Knowledge Base page of the GREENGAGE website.

For more details on training program, its preparation, training activities and materials, please refer to a deliverable D3.2, chapter 7.

4.2 Ethics

As overseen by the GREENGAGE Ethics Board and led by UWE, the project's ethical framework underpins the design and implementation of materials and systems, sets ethical standards for onboarding practices, and ratifies adherence to ethical standards expected by UWE, DEUSTO, and BUAS' respective ethics committees.

Ethics is core to GREENGAGE's mission and thus the first train-the-trainer session focussed solely on this. Led by UWE, partners from across the consortium were elucidated on the ethical documentation (from WP1) and engaged in discussion about particular areas of consideration. For a more in-depth breakdown of the training session, and accompanying material, please refer to D3.2.

As outlined above, the Equalities, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) principles informed the onboarding approaches, and the Ethics Starter Kit (Personal Consent Forms, Participant Information Sheet, and Privacy Notice) is a core component of the onboarding materials.

4.3 Training Materials

As part of WP4, a template was created for technology partners to profile their GREENGAGE Toolbox contributions, a component of the GREEN Engine. The standardised template captured key information such as:

- Name: Clear descriptor of the tool/component
- Description: Overview of functionality and purpose
- Usage Examples: Real-world applications in observatories
- Documentation: Installation guides, configuration instructions, API details
- Support: User forums, help channels
- Interoperability: Integration with other data and systems
- APIs & Interfaces: Endpoints, data formats, protocols
- Security & Privacy: Encryption, access control, data protections

Software tool or knowledge resource specification template

Name	Provide a clear and descriptive name for the component/resource.
URL	Indicates official URL where more detailed information about the resource can be found.
Description / abstract (1-2 paragraphs)	Include a comprehensive description of its purpose, functionality, and how it contributes to Citizen Observatories. This information helps users understand the component's role in the system
Snapshots	Images representing what the resource / component looks like and/or what it does
Authorship	Indicates who or what organization has created such resource
Audience	Check Audience field in https://eu-citizen.science/resources
Date creation	Indicate the date when the resource/component was declared
Date modified	Last date when changes were performed to the resource/component. N/A when resource / component is first declared.
Latest updates	Summarizes changes / upgrades performed to the resource. N/A when resource / component is first declared.
Keywords	Folksonomy created by those publishing new tools/resources to GREENGAGE catalogue.
Category	Check Category field in https://eu-citizen.science/resources
License	License upon which resource can be used
Publisher	Name of organization publishing the resource / component
Date published	Date of resource / component publication
Theme	Check Theme field in https://eu-citizen.science/resources
Languages	Check Language field in https://eu-citizen.science/resources
DOI	Only if applicable to the resource or component, otherwise N/A
Nature	It might be “Internal software”, “External software”, “Internal knowledge” and “External knowledge”. We could define new categories such as “training material”, “dissemination material” and so on. Overlaps with Category.
Problem profile	Related to keywords with fixed taxonomy. We should consider defining a taxonomy of Citizen Observatory terms and categories. Possibly merge with “Metadata & Discovery” field
Usage Examples (1-2 pages)	Include practical usage examples that demonstrate how the component/resource can be utilized within a Citizen Observatory empowered by GREENGAGE. Showcase real-world scenarios to help users understand the component's potential applications and benefits. Provide sufficient details for a developer or CO adopter to be able to use without your direct support the tool or resource made available. Include all the source code, initialization scripts and so on.
Documentation (3-5 pages)	Ensure comprehensive documentation is available, including installation guides, configuration instructions, API documentation, and usage examples. It should include the following sub-sections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview • Instructions • Reviews • Related resources

The format of the profiles informed the data structure needed for the Knowledge Base, a centralised space to share documentation along with user manuals, technical quick-starts, demo videos, and guided tutorials.

The overall aim is to lower barriers to adoption for citizen observers by transparently detailing the citizen science method in general and participation requirements and expectations in particular, outlining the common ground rules for data collection, providing an overview of the core functionalities of offered tools with their use in practice, along the tangible examples of their combined uses, and the intended use of the resulting outcomes.

Drawing upon these detailed profiles, each of the COs could make informed assessments on suitable tools as part of their Citizen Observatory journeys.

5 GREENGAGE Toolbox

GREENGAGE Toolbox (also referred as CO Toolbox) is part of the GREEN Engine and one of the facilitators of the GREENGAGE Academy. It includes open datasets generated, new open-source tools developed, manuals and HOWTOs developed through the Citizen Observatories. It serves as the central outward-facing communication platform for the GREENGAGE project and as a hub for project-related content made for the public dissemination. It is where project developments and updates are shared, materials are published. It comprises the set of tools created within GREEN Engine. Also, it is an entry point for potential Citizen Observatory participants to learn about and join a Citizen Observatory. Beyond supporting existing COs, a core goal of the GREENGAGE Toolbox is to enable interested participants to establish their own observatories, by providing helpful information and resources.

To better achieve this objective, the GREENGAGE website has been thoroughly reconstructed to make its offerings more accessible to a general audience. This overhaul involved three main phases:

Design - The site architecture, layouts, and components were reimaged in Figma to optimize the user experience for clarity, simplicity, and visualization. Emphasis was placed on surfacing the most critical information and entry points in an intuitive manner. Each pilot fed in with their own requirements, and constraints, to ensure communication was relevant, clear, and accessible as possible.

Development - With the designs complete, various WordPress plugins were researched to identify optimal technical solutions for the defined requirements. This informed the implementation of the redesigned site.

Content - To populate the refreshed website, the team aggregated relevant GREENGAGE deliverables, publications, manuals, multimedia assets, and other materials to serve as a Knowledge Base.

The updated website includes the Knowledge Base and signposts to complimentary external resources. The goal is to facilitate joining existing COs for interested people as well as supporting people to establish new COs within their communities.

5.1.1 Starting Point

The original GREENGAGE website primarily focused on communicating details about the project itself, including its high-level goals, partners involved, and the pilot regions. As such, the Home and About pages, shown below, outlined these core details about the project and consortium.

STRENGTHENING URBAN GOVERNANCE BY PROMOTING CITIZEN-BASED CO-CREATION AND CROWD-SOURCING

GREENGAGE is a 3-year long pan-European Innovation Action funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme. Consortium, led by Austrian Institute of Technology, consists of 17 research and industry partners from the EU and the UK.

GREENGAGE aims to **promote innovative governance process and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies**. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leverages citizens' participation and equips them with innovative digital solutions that will transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

OBJECTIVES

- Raise citizens' awareness, interest, and engagement in urban environmental issues
- Provide scientifically-sound and rigorous methods for citizen understanding of environmental data
- Promote and ensure broader acceptance and implementation rates of data collected by citizens in policy- and decision-making
- Promote the co-creation of data solutions for the urban environment
- Establish synergies among partner cities, with other Citizen Observatories and environmental agencies to exchange best practices, ensure transferability, uptake, and replication of successful Citizen Observatory experiences

CITIZEN OBSERVATORIES

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens are inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments and by developing Citizen Observatories towards complementing, validating and enriching the existing information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This enhanced and evidence-based information will be used for smart urban governance including policy evaluation, policymaking and decision-making.

The envisioned campaigns are to be deployed and fully demonstrated in four pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano – Gerace (Italy) and the region of Noord-Brabant (the Netherlands). These use cases aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, gathering new data which will complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policy-making.

BRISTOL
UNITED KINGDOM

COPENHAGEN
DENMARK

NOORD-BRABANT
THE NETHERLANDS

TURANO-GERACE
ITALY

OUR MISSION / INITIATIVE

GREENGAGE's mission is to promote innovative governance and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens will be inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The aim is to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies.

WHO WE ARE

The project brings together 14 partners from 8 countries: Austria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Italy, the Netherlands, Spain, Switzerland, United Kingdom.

While this oriented visitors to what GREENGAGE was about, the website architecture and content did not optimally guide citizens interested to practically get involved with COs. The priority needed to be shifted to enabling the formation of Citizen Observatories.

After extensive planning and coordination activities within the consortium, the focus of the members and pilots shifted to the next project stages centred on citizen participation and research. There was now a need to update the GREENGAGE website to directly support these upcoming objectives in two main ways:

1. Providing clear pathways for GREENGAGE observers to learn about, join, and contribute data to existing Citizen Observatory pilots. This included customizing certain website areas to match specific individual pilot visions, situational context, personnel, languages, and focus areas.
2. Publishing the "How to Do Research" training materials and CO tool documentation that had been developed.

A core part of the site overhaul was thus enhancing discoverability and access to these participation avenues and educational offerings. Additionally, an aim was to establish the GREENGAGE site as an ongoing, sustainable resource that could inform and empower community science beyond the timeline of the funded project itself.

5.1.2 Design Process

With foundational pilot definition from WP2 and knowledge of materials from WP3 and WP4 in hand, the contents to be communicated through the website were now apparent. Equipped with this understanding, GREENGAGE teams from KWMC, VRVIS, and AIT collaboratively evaluated the existing website architecture and language.

The focus was on striking the right balance between:

- Universal accessibility through plain language content;
- Intuitive intra-website navigation; and
- Targeted pilot-specific communication suited to their communities.

The process emphasised discoverability for the diverse audience groups.

Each pilot fed in their requirements and outlined their use of existing technical platforms and preferred outreach methods. This helped shape functional needs for customised pilot landing areas.

Research of comparable community science websites like WeObserve and the Bristol Approach informed content structure and phrasing standards that have resonated across initiatives.

With foundational planning complete, the collective insights drove the execution of the new information structure to enable intuitive navigation.

Structure

The first area of focus was evaluating the site's structural composition - its information architecture and navigational nomenclature. In its original form, the site organisation and terminology centred around formal project details. For example, the main menu reflected internal consortium terms like "Pilots" and difficult to distinguish sections such as "Resources" and "GREENGAGE Toolbox"; the content followed suit, through its focus on high-level project objectives.

Feedback pointed to three priority concepts that needed emphasis and clarification:

Citizen Observatories and role of a Citizen Observer - The COs represent a cornerstone of community-led science within GREENGAGE, but the existing "Pilots" menu item obfuscated this.

GREENGAGE Academy, Collaborative Environment – As one of the project's core values is enabling Citizen Observers to participate in the thematic co-exploration, through accessing GREENGAGE tools and knowledge assets.

Knowledge Base – It was recognised that a word "Resources" do not cover well the materials that will be placed there. As "Knowledge Base" is an already established and widely recognised term, all of the supporting content from Work Packages could be consolidated there, along with other media originally found under Resources, such as scientific and non-scientific publications and other promotional material. This would provide clarity and differentiation from the GREENGAGE Academy where access to Collaborative Environment will be provided.

In response, the new structure should feature these differentiators more prominently, and the site content should provide clear explanations to set context and orient new visitors. The goal was to embrace what makes GREENGAGE unique, whilst demystifying any new language being introduced.

As the pilots now had clearer definitions, it was apparent that the two Italian pilots should be separated out into distinct Citizen Observatories, and each of the CO pages tailored to their audiences.

The original website's content relating to the GREENGAGE project itself is still important and valuable to feature but could now live on the page under a phrase "What is GREENGAGE?", an intuitive location for such information.

Through these information architecture and navigation adjustments, the aim was to craft an intuitive journey for Observatory participants to discover GREENGAGE's core strengths, idiosyncratic pathways for participation, and resources aligned with project priorities.

Prototype in Figma

Once the structure was agreed upon, GREENGAGE partners from AIT, VRVIS, and KWMC carried out a number of group sessions, using Figma¹ as a creative, collaborative environment for prototyping. Taking

¹ Figma: The Collaborative Interface Design Tool (<https://www.figma.com/>)

inspiration from previous related projects and established designs, gathering feedback from pilots and potential users, the group created mock-ups of potential layouts until consensus was found and it was ready to be implemented.

5.2 Updated Website Structure

The simplicity of this new structure reflects the work of WP2 and champions GREENGAGE’s contributions to Citizen Science: Citizen Observatories, the Knowledge Base, and the GREENGAGE Academy, whilst retaining a central place for all related Events, and a space to communicate about the GREENGAGE project in a wider sense.

This clarity of communication informed the focus of the rest of the site content.

As an example, the previous header “Strengthening Urban Governance By Promoting Citizen-Based Co-Creation And Crowd-Sourcing” was replaced with the clearer and more direct official branding tagline.

5.2.1 Citizen Observatories

With ‘Citizen Observatories’ given priority in the structure, it was important to demystify this term up-front, and therefore the top of the landing page now focuses on introducing, explaining, and grounding this term for new visitors.

GREENGAGE project sets out to help public authorities shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives.

To achieve this, the project aims at developing **Citizen Observatories (CO)** focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living for the delivery of carbon neutral neighbourhoods. The developed Citizen Observatories are supported by **bespoke digital technologies and tools** that facilitate citizens’ participation in observing, sensing, and monitoring their urban environments and co-developing innovative solutions to pressing environmental problems.

Findings are used to influence urban governance including policy evaluation, policy making and decision making at the city level.

Citizen Observatories

Citizen Observatories (CO) are initiatives that empower citizens to actively participate in the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data to address various issues affecting their communities and contribute to policy-making and community development.

Five **Citizen Observatories (CO)** based at four different European cities and regions (pilots) are used to create

Alongside the explanatory guidance, there is an interactive map showing the geographical locations of each CO with each clickable to give a quick, intuitive routes to relevant visitors. Specifically, once the circular markers on the map are clicked on, the visitors are redirected to the individual CO pages, adding to the user-friendly nature of the GREENGAGE website. The map shows all five GREENGAGE pilot locations: Bristol, Copenhagen, Turano, Gerace and North Brabant. Further the visitor will find definitions and directions how to access GREEN Engine, Knowledge Base, Planned and Future Events as well as link to more information about the consortium.

Once clicking on the “Become a Citizen Observer!”, user is redirected to the page where Citizen Observatories are presented, with further explained Citizen Observatory Journey and links to the GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories themselves. It also gives a quick access for a user who is interested in becoming a Citizen Observer by clicking on a button “Become a Citizen Observer!”.

Bristol
United Kingdom

Copenhagen
Denmark

North Brabant
The Netherlands

Turano
Italy

Gerace
Italy

GREENGAGE has pilot engagements in **5 selected European cities and regions**. Each of these pilots employ use cases which target different EU Green Deal objectives. These use cases aim to highlight the areas where smart city governance is mostly needed.

Scope

GREENGAGE develops Citizen Observatories (COs) to promote the active engagement of citizens in the collection and use of localised knowledge and intelligence used in urban development and decision-making. **Citizens are invited to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their neighbourhoods in terms of air quality, mobility, and well-being.** Their participation will be enhanced and supported by **innovative technologies** through wearables or proprietary devices and apps).

With the help of technology, citizens' participation will help generate new crowdsourced data to:

- o complement, validate, and enrich information held by the public administrations and/or environment agencies derived from remote sensing data and obtained via other authoritative observations
- o improve urban governance by providing evidence for policy evaluation, policy making and decision making
- o increase societal awareness by showcasing the environmental challenges (climate change, poor air quality, healthy living)

Journey

Once clicking on one of the listed locations, a user is redirected to a unique and individualised page dedicated for the chosen CO. The page lists upcoming planned and past events organised in relation to the chosen CO. A filtered version of Events featuring those relevant to the CO as well as overall GREENGAGE project events. Below, citizens can use the form to express interest in joining a CO, and this will be updated for participants to sign up fully when COs are ready. Further, each of these individualised pages offers essential information on the pilot itself, its CO(s), identified challenges, the overview of the use cases, and the reasoning of why is pilot undertaking the related initiatives. It also

provides an interactive explanation about the Citizen Observer Journey, showing the onboarding, and explaining in simple steps processes of data collection, analysis and evaluation that CO can take part in.

Upcoming Events in Bristol

Past Events

- 17
BRISTOL CITIZENS OBSERVATORY ACTIVATION WORKSHOP
NOV
[Find out more »](#)
- 17
2ND PROJECT MEETING
OCT
[Find out more »](#)

other GREENGAGE events

GREENGAGE

[Citizen Observatories](#) | [Knowledge Base](#) | [GREEN Engine](#) | [Events](#) | [About](#)

Rolling out two Liveable Neighbourhood pilot projects are Mayoral priorities for Bristol, with the **East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood being the first scheme to be piloted in the city**. The West of England Combined Authority (WECA) has provided funding to use an area-wide approach to develop a Low Traffic Neighbourhood (Liveable Neighbourhood), rather than just design linear infrastructure for route improvements.

The project area covers parts of five wards of Bristol: Lawrence Hill, Easton, St George West, St George Central and St George Troopers Hill, south of Church Road and north of the River Avon. Recently, in January 2024, Bristol Administration approved to advertise the Traffic Regulation Order (TRO) for the full EBLN scheme. It is due to begin late January.

Identified challenges

- A **climate and ecological emergency** articulated by local and national plans require widespread citizen participation to deliver the set goals of social-ecological transformation in the city. The pilot's work within the EBLN is supporting BCC's ambition of becoming Carbon Neutral by 2030.
- LN schemes offer a promising pathway for community-led urban transformation beyond the pilot's area of intervention if they are recognized and accepted by local communities and municipalities. However, **Liveable Neighbourhoods have been controversial in some areas of the country** where they have been introduced rapidly. The most successful schemes of this nature are delivered in partnership with and at the pace of the local community.
- As the pilot starts, the EBLN team has already been working with the community and other stakeholders for two years and realised the "Co-Discovery" and "Co-Design" stages of their process. They intend to use the GREENGAGE methodology on COs to **re-engage with the community** to re-iterate the first stages and to deliver the "Trial" stage using the GREEN Engine and toolbox.
- At the time when their GREENGAGE CO Activation was supposed to happen, the pilot owners couldn't start the re-engagement due to Barton house evacuation, that is at the heart of the pilot area and "communication shutdown" in East Bristol, demanded by BCC.
- Bristol City Council will face **changes due to the municipal governance shift** from a mayor to a committee system. The change in governance structure will be effective from May 2024. The EBLN programme is required to reflect timescales associated with the Pre-Election Period (PEP) which runs from March, as well as the formation of the new Committee System.

Bristol's Citizen Observatory

The pilot project seeks **feedback and input from the local community** to help design a re-imagined streetscape that realises the vision set through the Citizen Assembly. The Liveable Neighbourhoods Team envisions at least **two GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories**.

The first CO will give the possibility to re-engage with the local community, especially with those members of the local community who were concerned about the scheme and its trial interventions. Through means of engagement that go beyond data collection, the pilot owners will seek to discover issues of shared concern (around journeys, traffic displacement, perception of and actual safety, air quality/pollution, opportunities for increased green infrastructure etc) amongst participants and support them to envision their neighbourhoods together. Grounding the CO in issues that still matter to the people is important for rebuilding trust in BCC and ensuring participation of historically underrepresented groups as well as supporting the co-design of forthcoming interventions that will be part of the second CO.

The second CO will consider the learnings from the 1st CO as well as the issues that need to be addressed to successfully deliver the 1st phase of the "trial" stage of the EBLN scheme as well as the metrics to evaluate GREENGAGE COs (as in WP6). Ensuring a representative participation, the pilot owners will attempt to monitor and explore the effects of the interventions performed by the EBLN scheme, in other words validate whether those interventions are delivering positive effects in line with policy objectives for a more equitable city, and just transition towards becoming climate neutral by 2030. This should inspire local authorities to adopt and adapt the scheme to the contexts of their neighbourhoods considering policy demands for climate mitigation.

Who we are?

The **Citizen Observatories (COs) in Bristol** will demand the involvement of different societal groups from beginning to end. People will not only contribute gathering data with devices or answering to surveys, but they will also help co-designing the hypothesis and associated experiments/campaigns to allow their validation or rebuttal.

GREENGAGE

[Citizen Observatories](#) | [Knowledge Base](#) | [GREEN Engine](#) | [Events](#) | [About](#)

What will we do?

Analyse and visualise impact of road closures on mobility patterns (journey quality)

The system will use historical mobility data and road closure data and analyse mobility patterns before and after road closures. It will also compare traffic flow, travel times, and congestion levels before and after road closures as well as identify any significant changes in mobility patterns and potential causes. It will visualise and report the results to stakeholders and decision-makers.

Possible steps:

- User opens visualisation tool
- User loads data for visualisation
- User selects analysis mode (mobility patterns, traffic flow, congestion levels etc)
- User downloads / exports analysis information (images, spreadsheets etc)

Air quality/ Environment monitoring

Monitor and visualise air quality of the neighbourhood at different times (e.g. at different times of the day, for different congestion levels etc).

Monitor environment and identify safety / threat levels

Analyse threat levels of various neighbourhoods and visualise for further analyses and input to policy-making.

Mobility Pattern Analysis to determine accessibility to shops, schools, services, and other local amenities

Use techniques such as GPS tracking and to determine routes that citizens take to local amenities and identify improvements. Categorise routes by mode of transport and analyse alternative travel modes.

Why?

- By partnering with local communities and especially empowering people from marginalised groups such as children and families in East Bristol to meaningfully participate in the co-creation of EBLN, the pilot expects to increase trust in the scheme and insights on the effects of interventions (e.g., removing cut through routes for non-local vehicle traffic) on local people's everyday lives.
- By preparing, testing, and evaluating the community-led performance of mitigation policies through EBLN, the pilot owners will gain understanding of success criteria of LN projects that will be shared through a Handbook for LN. Learnings will feed into of the city-wide scheme of Liveable Neighbourhoods and inform future plans, policies and strategies in the context of LN that are already planned for South Bristol.
- By engaging citizens and community anchor organisations not only through data collection but in various ways in urban planning processes, local interventions will become more responsive to concerns and visions expressed by local communities. This is expected to strengthen BCC's aspirations of enabling co-creation of liveable neighbourhoods together with the local population and should lead towards manifesting long-term citizen participation modes as integral part of municipal governance, e.g., through Citizen Assemblies which democratise urban planning and politicise citizen engagement.

5.2.2 Knowledge Base

The central point for hosting and sharing information is now termed the Knowledge Base, a place for all the materials developed in the training process, support and manuals for technical tools, and other content created in the project and to support COs.

In this First Iteration of the Knowledge Base, the categories are seen as above:

- Deliverables: All the deliverables submitted within GREENGAGE project that are meant to be publicly available;
- Publications: Any research publications and conference papers written during running of the project;
- Newsletter: News related to the activities organised within GREENGAGE project;
- Training Materials: Documentation about the tools that is meant to be accessed by Citizen Observers;
- Glossary of Terms: List of terms used in GREENGAGE, updated during the lifetime of the project;
- Multimedia: Videos, Presentations, Audios.

Once more material is created throughout the training process, this will be uploaded and live here too. A set of sub-categories is being developed which will inform the design of V2 (as discussed below).

5.2.3 GREENGAGE Academy, Collaborative Environment

Accessing GREENGAGE Academy brings users to the Collaborative Environment (CE), which is meant to be used by Citizen Observers to participate in the thematic co-exploration. It is the main point of entry to be part of a CO and consists of a template container which can be duplicated for each CO. It contains the full set of GREENGAGE tools and knowledge assets to run the Observatory self-sustained.

Currently the CE is available behind this link: www.demo.greengage-project.eu and will be accessible via the GREENGAGE Academy menu entry.

All the above is part of the GREEN Engine which is the sum of:

- The community and process management tools (i.e., CE)
- Discourse (the discussion platform)
- The GREENGAGE toolbox (tools to capture, curate, analyse and visualize data)

- Knowledge Assets aka. CO Enablers which provide materials, guidelines, trainings, templates and canvases to streamline the co-delivery of thematic co-explorations by the Citizen Observatories

5.2.4 Events

Events remains as an item in the parent hierarchy, but it has now been spread, integrated, and adapted further throughout the website. A brief overview of Upcoming Events now features on the landing page, as well as on each CO site which include filtering version showing only the events relevant to them and pulls in project-wide events.

This solves a few recognised earlier problems:

- CO pages are more focussed and relevant to their visitors.
- Events are now more prominent and easily discoverable for general visitors; the homepage gives a sense of dynamism with regular new activity. Additionally, for citizens only viewing their relevant CO section, project-wide events now play a more prominent role, encouraging wider-project interest whilst retaining CO relevancy.
- Events still have their own page giving an overview of all public project activity which allows following activities related to the entire GREENGAGE project.

GREENGAGE Become a Citizen Observer! Access GREENGAGE Academy Knowledge Base **Events** What is GREENGAGE?

Q Search for events **Find Events** List Month Day

< > Today February 20, 2023 - Now ▾

February 2023

MON 20 February 20, 2023 - February 22, 2023
GREENGAGE Project Kick-Off in Bristol
 University of the West of England Bristol (UWE) Bristol, United Kingdom
 The Horizon Europe project GREENGAGE has been kicked-off in Bristol (UK) on 20-21 February 2023. Led by the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH, 17 partners from 8 European countries [...]

June 2023

WED 7 June 7, 2023 @ 07:45 - 09:00
Bristol Business Breakfast
 Bristol Business School and Bristol Law School X Block Frenchay Campus
 Coldharbour Lane, Bristol, United Kingdom
 The Bristol Business Breakfast networking event took place on the 7 June 2023 at

5.2.5 “What is GREENGAGE?”

Finally, the page titled as “What is GREENGAGE?” hones the legacy content from the old website “About” page, combining the most pertinent and engaging aspects, whilst updating the language to reflect the current nomenclature, thus being less formal and therefore accessible.

GREENGAGE is a 3-year long pan-European Innovation Action funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, further co-funded by the UK government's Horizon Europe funding framework (UKRI) and Switzerland's State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Consortium, led by Austrian Institute of Technology, consists of 17 research and industry partners from the EU and the UK.

GREENGAGE aims to **promote innovative governance process and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies**. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leverages citizens' participation and equips them with innovative digital solutions thus providing the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions for monitoring environmental problems at ground level. The developed Citizen Observatories (CO) will be further incorporated into the urban planning decision-making process.

Objectives

- Raise citizens' awareness, interest, and engagement in urban environmental issues
- Provide scientifically-sound and rigorous methods for citizen understanding of environmental data
- Promote and ensure broader acceptance and implementation rates of data collected by citizens in policy- and decision-making
- Promote the co-creation of data solutions for the urban environment
- Establish synergies among partner cities, with other Citizen Observatories and environmental agencies to exchange best practices, ensure transferability, uptake, and replication of successful Citizen Observatory experiences

OUR MISSION / INITIATIVE

GREENGAGE's mission is to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by delivering **innovative governance models** and to harness the social and cultural opportunities by promoting **active engagement of citizens** in data collection and use of urban decision-making via Citizen Observatories (CO). By doing so, the project will **transform citizens' engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives** for carbon neutral cities.

WHO WE ARE

The project brings together 14 partners from 8 countries: Austria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Italy, the Netherlands, Spain, Switzerland, United Kingdom.

6 Next Steps

6.1.1 Expression of Interest

Each of the pilots is now collecting expressions of interests from citizens.

As covered elsewhere in the project, much work has been done on Ethics, led by UWE in WP1 (D1.9 and D1.11), to ensure only relevant information is being collected, and a system is being established to create unique identifiers that can't be cross-referenced by the consortium, ensuring that sensitive information needed for reporting and ensuring good representation can't be combined with personally identifying information.

USER GROUPS AND LOGINS

6.1.2 Workshops

The first set of workshops, as described in D3.3, will set out the aims of each CO and establish roles within those along with collectively decided upon thematic explorations, goals, and approaches.

6.1.3 Participant Surveys

Following the expressions of interests and initial workshops, citizens wanting to commit as part of a Citizen Observatory will be completing a more in-depth and formal participation survey.

The goal is to make this as straight forward as possible for people, with sections only appearing when relevant, and breaking the form into multiple parts as not to overwhelm people.

6.1.4 Expanding the Knowledge Base

A second stage of the Knowledge Base will be designed to make the content searchable and filterable, once again using Figma as a collaborative design environment. A set of sub-categories is being developed which will be used to form the schema of the data.

7 Conclusions

A two-step approach to training, starting with Train-the-Trainer, helps to build capacity within the consortium and enables pilot leads to pull from expertise within the project whilst tailoring approaches to suit their specific COs.

The interplay of specialised groups, such as the Innovation Action Board, Pilot Support Teams, and Ethics Board shows the strengths of collaboration and provides a usable model for future Citizen Observatories.

A solid foundation has been developed with the new website, that has room to grow with the project, and is built to live on and evolve beyond the life of the project.